

DISCURSIVE ANALYSIS OF THE TEXT OF THE FAIRY TALE GENRE

Nazarova Nurjahon Bahodirovna

PhD Student of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Email: nurjahonn@gmail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7558440>

Annotation This article provides information on the structural analysis of the fairy tale genre, its division into initial formulas, medial formulas, and final formulas, and the purpose of using these formulas and their role in the fairy tale text. In addition, examples of fairy-tale formulas were given, an opinion was made about the changes of these formulas according to the type of fairy-tale, and information was given about the opinions expressed by our research scientists about the structural structure of the text of the fairy-tale genre.

Key words: Household Tales, Fantasy Adventure Tales, Animal Tales, Initial Formulas, Medial Formulas, Final Formulas

Аннотация Ушбу мақолада эртак жанри матнининг структурал таҳлили унинг инициал формулалар, медиал формулалар, финал формулаларга ажратилиши ва ушбу формулаларнинг қўлланилиши мақсади ва эртак матнида тутган ўрни ҳақида маълумот берилган. Бундан ташқари, эртак формулаларига мисоллар келтирилиб, эртак тури асносида ушбу формулалар ўзгариб бориши ҳақида фикр олиб борилган бўлиб, қолаверса тадқиқотчи олимларимиз томонидан эртак жанри матнининг структурал тузилиши ҳақида билдирган мулоҳазалари ҳақида маълумот берилган.

Калит сўзлар: Маиший эртаклар, фантастик саргузаит эртак, ҳайвонлар ҳақидаги эртак, инициал формулалар, медиал формулалар, финал формулалар

Аннотация В данной статье представлены сведения о структурном анализе жанра сказки, его разделении на начальные формулы, медиальные формулы и конечные формулы, а также о цели использования этих формул и

их роли в тексте сказки. Кроме того, были приведены примеры сказочных формул, высказано мнение об изменениях этих формул по типу сказки, а также дана информация о мнениях, высказанных нашими учеными-исследователями о структурной структуре текста. жанра сказки.

Ключевые слова: Бытовые сказки, фантастические приключенческие сказки, сказки о животных, начальные формулы, средние формулы, окончательные формулы

Nowadays we cannot imagine our fast-paced lives without technology, we can observe that the need for fairy tales among our youth is waning. However, reading fairy tales has a broad and positive influence on the intellectual potential, psyche and imagination of our youngsters, who are the hopes of our lives.

We got our first ideas about the universe that surrounds us through fairy tales. For this reason, even though the text of the fairy tale has been studied to this day, we feel the urge to study it more deeply. It is known that a fairy tale is one of the main types of oral creativity, a fictional story of a fantastic adventure and nature. In stories of animal, animals can communicate like humans, and each animal has its own character.

For example, the fox is cunning, the bear is lazy, the rabbit is cowardly, etc. Most of the heroes of household tales are "farmer", "shoemaker", "old man", "orphan boy", "tanna girl". Fairy tale scholar N. Roshianu told about the structure of fairy tales

- a) Initial formulas
- b) Medial formulas
- c) Final formulas.

This type of divisibility is based on the formal position of these elements in the fairy tale text (Roshianu 1974.16). Repetition of traditional formulas determines the actions of the fairy tale, their structural features and gives them specific functions.

N.N. Dostkhodjaeva stated that "the artistic perfection of a fairy tale begins with its introduction (initial "zachin")." According to M. Afzalov, "These traditional

divisions depend on the artistic skill of the fairy tale. The purpose of giving examples of different versions of zachins is to show the skills of word artists in choosing words.

K.Imomov, doctor of philological sciences, says, "In a fairy tale, the beginning is a permanent element in the plot line, but it is not related to the development of the plot, it does not give impetus to the organization of the action. It provides information about the characters involved, indicates the time and place in which the events that are supposed to happen in the plot line will take place.

The beginning always acquires uncertainty and generality in the direction of the plot" (Imomov K. 1981). Q. Beknazarov notes the following about the beginning of fairy tales: "Initial formulas are traditional ornaments in fairy tales, usually performing the task of attracting the listener's attention to the epic space and time or the traditional introduction to the fairy tale" (Q. Beknazarov 1993).

Bir bor ekan bir yo'q ekan. Qadim qadim zamonda tuyalar dallol ekan, pashsha sartarosh ekan.

In addition to attracting the listener's attention, the introduction of a fairy tale performs aesthetic tasks such as creating an imaginary background that matches the nature of the plot and creating uplifting and happy moods among the listeners of the fairy tale (Kholmurodova O.A 2020).

Bir bor ekan, bir yo'q ekan, och ekanda, to'q ekan, bo'ri bokavul ekan, tulki yasovul ekan, qarg'a qaqimchi ekan, chumchuq chaqimchi ekan, g'oz karnaychi ekan, o'rdak surnaychi ekan, tovuq toq etdi bilmadim qayga ketdi.....

In the process of studying the text of folk tales, the initial formulas mainly indicate that the event took place in the long past.

Qadim zamonda.... Burungi zamonda , Long ago...,once upon a time, there was once a,

"In the initial parts of the fairy tales, the concept of the hero, time and space is constantly repeated at the level of legitimacy. Also, the elements of whether or not the event happened are constant" (Dostkhodjaeva N.N 1999).

In the text of Uzbek fairy tales, in many cases, we can find more imaginary and fictional beginnings.

Men otamning beshigini tebratib o'tirgan bir zamonda bir podshox bor ekan.

"It is known that there is a lot of information about the fact that the performer of a fairy tale directly affects the text of the fairy tale by his verb, profession, age, gender, and mental state. Therefore, if the verb of the storyteller does not accept excessive details, he will transfer the medial part of the story to the content expression as soon as he has briefly stated it. If the storyteller has the ability to perfectly describe the details of each event, then the medial part of the story will be perfect in turn," says Dostkhodjaeva N.N. Medial formulas differ from each other (Bakanova A.V 2006). Medial formulas vary according to the content of the tale. Medial formulas also refer to the passing of one event to another.

Endi ikki og'iz so'zni.....dan eshiting.

What is more, medial structure expresses time expressions.

Kundan-kun, Oydan-oy, yildan-yil o'tibdi.

The final formulas in both Uzbek and English fairy tales express a happy ending, admonition, and the regret of the heroes of the fairy tale.

Shunday qilib, ota-qiz murod maqsadlariga yetishibdi She decided always to follow her mother's advice

In short, the initial formula of the fairy tale consists of repeated ornaments, the purpose of its use is to give the fairy tale an upbeat spirit and attract the listener's attention. Medial formulas expand according to the desire of the storyteller and the scope of his imagination.

Адабиётлар

1. Достходжаева Н.Н Ўзбек сеҳрли эртакларининг структурал таҳлили .Дисс...канд.филол. наук. -Тошкент, 1999. -20 б.
2. Рошияну 1974.16
3. Баканова А.В 2006
4. Холмуродова О.А 2020

5. Қ.Бекназаров . Ўзбек халқ маиший эртаклари ўрганилиши: таснифи, поэтикаси. .Дисс...канд.филол. наук.-Т.:1993.15-бет.
6. Имомов К. Ўзбек халқ эртаклари. Т.1981.25 б
7. Alisherovna, M. N., Furqatovna, S. Y., & kizi, K. Z. K. (2022). Principles for determining the categories of proximity of the Russian language to Uzbek in the field of phraseology: Identification of interlingual phraseological accordance. *International Journal of Health Sciences*, 6(S5), 1414²1419.
8. Абдувахабова У. Экспрессивно-стилистические и художественные особенности авторского стиля герберта бейтса //Иностранная филология: язык, литература, образование. – 2021. – №. 3 (80). – С. 28-33.
9. Ibodullayeva M. H. The use of superstitions in the life of English speaking countries and their types according to situations //Samarkand: So'z san'ati. – 2022. – С. 2-3.
10. Karimova S. V. Strategies for expanding students' vocabulary in ESL lessons //Science and Education. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 730-736.
11. Назарова Н. Б. ЭРТАКНИНГ ДИСКУРСИВ БЕЛГИЛАРИ //МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА. – 2022. – Т. 5. – №. 2.
12. Пулатова Ф. А. Талабаларни танқидий фикрлашга ўргатиш ва педагогик ёндашиш //Science and Education. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 822-825.
13. Furkatovna S. Y. Modern methods and approaches for effective distance learning of English language //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 500-504.
14. Khamraeva Z. K. The problem with the four conditionals or causality in english //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 10. – С. 1428-1433.
15. Bakhodirovna K. F. The Importance of TPR (Total Physical Response) Method in Teaching English for beginners //Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching. – 2022. – Т. 8. – С. 156-158.
16. Холикова Л. Ф. MANAGING UNIVERSITY STUDENTS'RESEARCH SKILLS THROUG INTERDISCIPLINARY PROJECTS AND E-PROJECTS

//МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА. – 2021. – Т. 4. – №. 4.

17. Kholmurodovna K. D., Valieva K. S. DEVELOPING SPEAKING ABILITIES OF LEARNERS BY ENRICHING THEIR VOCABULARY OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE //Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 09. – С. 6-10.
18. Юлдашева С. Важность использования различных педагогических технологий на уроках //Результаты научных исследований в условиях пандемии (COVID-19). – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 04. – С. 126-128.